

NAVIGATING MIGRAINE MANAGEMENT IN THE MENSTRUAL AGE GROUP: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW OF CURRENT EVIDENCE

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ABSTRACT

Background- A large percentage of people suffer from migraines, and women in their menstrual age group exhibit unique patterns. This review sheds light on the relationship between hormonal changes and migraine pathogenesis by exploring the prevalence rates and associated factors influencing migraine presentation in this population. **Objective-** This study examines the relationship between migraine and menstrual cycle, providing researchers and physicians with insights into the distinct features, prevalence, causes, and therapy approaches of migraine in individuals who are menstruation. **Methodology-** Several databases, including PubMed, Scopus, Research Gate, Google Scholar, and the Cochrane Library, were thoroughly searched to find pertinent articles on migraine and homoeopathic treatment for the systematic review. High-calibre observational studies and randomised controlled trials will be chosen based on predetermined inclusion criteria. The synthesis and extraction of data will adhere to accepted standards for systematic reviews. **Result-** Ten studies (n=10) on understanding prevalence and distribution were included out of the total 144 research articles that were included for the review. Ten (n=10) were evaluated to comprehend modern science treatment, and seven (n=7) to comprehend homoeopathic treatment. **Conclusion -** The review highlights the need of customised homoeopathic treatment for the management of migraine headaches in the menstrual age range. It also advocates for cooperation between practitioners of complementary and conventional medicine as well as more research to verify the treatment's safety and efficacy.

KEYWORDS:

Migraine, periodic attacks, menstrual migraine, menstruation, homoeopathy, homoeopathic similimum.

INTRODUCTION:

Migraine headaches among the menstrual age group, typically defined as ages ranging from adolescence to menopause, represent a significant health concern due to their high prevalence and profound impact on daily functioning. Studies suggest that around 60-70% of women with migraines report a relationship between their headaches and their menstrual cycles, particularly around menstruation.^{1,2} Common symptoms experienced during menstrual migraines include pulsating or throbbing head pain, often unilateral, accompanied by nausea, vomiting, and heightened sensitivity to light, sound, or smells. The severity and duration of these symptoms can vary, with some individuals experiencing debilitating attacks lasting for days.^{3,4,5} Moreover, menstrual migraines can be associated with unique complications, including menstrual-related mood disturbances such as premenstrual syndrome (PMS) or premenstrual dysphoric disorder (PMDD), which may exacerbate migraine symptoms and decrease quality of life. Additionally, hormonal fluctuations during the menstrual cycle can contribute to increased migraine susceptibility and severity, making management challenging. Compounding this complexity, menstrual migraines often coexist with other menstrual-related disorders, such as endometriosis or polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS), further complicating diagnosis and treatment.^{6,7,8,9} Given the significant burden of menstrual migraines on individuals' lives and healthcare systems, a comprehensive understanding of their prevalence, symptoms, and associated complications is essential for effective management and improved quality of life for those affected.¹⁰

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Allopathic treatments for migraine headaches in the menstrual age group primarily focus on alleviating symptoms and preventing attacks. Common medications include nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), triptans, and hormonal therapies such as estrogenic supplements or contraceptive pills. While these treatments can provide significant relief, they are not without their adverse effects.

NSAIDs may cause gastrointestinal discomfort, while triptans can lead to sensations of tingling or tightness.^{11,12} Hormonal therapies may carry risks of thromboembolic events or hormonal fluctuations, potentially exacerbating migraine symptoms in some individuals. Additionally, long-term use of medications may result in medication-overuse headaches, further complicating management. Thus, careful consideration of both the benefits and risks of allopathic treatments is essential in tailoring management strategies for migraine in the menstrual age group.^{13,14,15}

In the management of migraine within the menstrual age group, the homoeopathic principle of individual constitution plays a pivotal role. By understanding each patient's unique constitution, including physical, mental, and emotional traits, homoeopathy tailors treatment to address the underlying causes of migraine. This personalized approach not only aims to alleviate symptoms but also seeks to restore balance within the individual, thereby reducing the frequency and intensity of migraines. Through the application of homoeopathic remedies aligned with the patient's constitution, this holistic approach offers promising avenues for effective migraine management in menstruating individuals.^{16,17}

Homeopathic management offers a holistic approach to migraine headaches in menstrual age groups, focusing on addressing the root cause of the condition. Remedies like Belladonna, Lachesis, and Sepia target hormonal imbalances, stress factors, and menstrual cycle triggers. Homeopathic treatments have minimal side effects, enhancing overall well-being.

METHODOLOGY:

1. Search area- the literature about migraine headache, Homoeopathic principles and philosophy, and homoeopathic medicine was done.

2. Search engine – various search engines like Scopus, PubMed, Web of Science, Research Gate and Google Scholar were used.

The Bharti Vidyapeeth (DTU) Homoeopathic Medical College and Bharti Vidyapeeth (DTU) Medical College libraries' printed literature was reviewed.

3. Literature search – A systematic strategy is necessary to perform a thorough literature search on migraine in the menstrual age group, covering its epidemiology and the effectiveness of both allopathic and homoeopathic treatments. First, pertinent Medical Subject Headings (MeSH) terms and keywords would be used to query databases like PubMed, MEDLINE, Cochrane Library, and Embase. Boolean operators like "AND," "OR," and "NOT" would be used to refine the search and identify pertinent research. Examples of these phrases could be "migraine," "menstrual migraine," "epidemiology," "hormonal fluctuations," "occupational factors," "allopathic treatment," and "homoeopathic treatment." Furthermore, publication date, study design, and language filters can be used to guarantee that only the most recent, excellent research is included. To find unpublished research and reports, grey literature sources such as institutional repositories and conference proceedings will also be investigated. Every aspect of the search strategy, including the databases examined, the search words used, and any inclusion/exclusion criteria employed, would be well documented. The automated search procedure would also be enhanced by manual reference list searches from recognised literature and expert consultation. A thorough grasp of migraine epidemiology and the relative efficacy of allopathic and homoeopathic treatments across the menstrual age range can be obtained by using a strict and methodical approach to literature search.

4. Data extraction- The available English-language research articles pertaining to migraine investigations in the menstrual age range were consulted for data extraction. The data was gathered independently by two authors, and it was verified and cross-checked by three more authors. The information gathered included: (1) Author, (2)Year; (3) Methodology; and (4) Conclusion (n=144).

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5. **Study selection** – Inclusion Strategy: For this review, a thorough search of manuscripts on migrants in menstruation age groups published between 2019 and 2024 was conducted.

Exclusion criteria: 1. Duplicates 2. Irrelevant, publication with a language other than English.

RESULTS:

Studies on migraines in menstruating age groups uncover the pathophysiology of migraines and hormonal swings, with a heightened occurrence and intensity during particular cycles. Pharmacological therapies, lifestyle modifications, and hormone regulation are examples of management techniques.

Table 1. migraine in today's light

Migraine In Today's Light				
Sl.no	Title	Author	year of publication	conclusion
1	Sex differences in prevalence of migraine trigger factors: A cross-sectional study	Daphne S van Casteren <i>et.all</i>	2020	Migraine Trigger Factors in Women <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More provocative migraine attacks than men. • Possible lower migraine threshold due to sex hormonal changes.
2	Between and within-woman differences in the association between menstruation and migraine days	James S. McGinley <i>et.all</i>	2021	Study on Menstrual-Related Migraine <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Elevated odds of migraine days from day -2 to day +3. • Effect of menses on migraine days varies within-woman. • Provides foundation for understanding menstrual-related migraine from individual patient's perspective.

3	Acute and Preventive Management of Migraine during Menstruation and Menopause	Raffaele Ornello <i>et.all</i>	2021	<p>Course and Treatments of Migraine</p> <p>Periodic migraine (MM) is a unique clinical entity because of increased sensitivity to migraine related to oestrogen levels. • Menstrual migraine (MM) is influenced by female reproductive milestones, including menstruation and perimenopause.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Long-acting triptans, shortterm prophylaxis, combined hormonal contraceptives, and conventional preventive are the treatments for perimenopausal migraine and MM. When treating women with perimenopausal migraine, hormonal therapies should try to prevent variations in oestrogen levels. • Future studies will examine the relationship between migraine aetiology mechanisms and female sex hormones.
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5	Sex Hormones and Calcitonin Gene-Related Peptide in Women With Migraine A Cross-sectional, Matched Cohort Study	Bianca Raffaelli <i>et.all</i>	2023	<p>Sex Hormone Profiles and Migraine • CGRP concentrations may vary.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Menstruation capacity and migraines may influence CGRP levels. • CGRP measurement in tear fluid feasible.

6	Brain structural and functional differences between pure menstrual migraine and menstrually-related migraine	Tao Xu <i>et.all</i>	2020	<p>Study on MRM and PMM Patients</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Significant difference in spontaneous neural activity in DLPFC and mPFC between MRM and PMM. • Positive correlation between ALFF values in mPFC and CGRP expression in PMM patients. • New approach investigates central mechanisms differences. • Elucidates relationship between neural abnormalities and CGRP expression in PMM individuals.
7	Allodynia in Menstrually Related Migraine: Score Assessment by Allodynia Symptom Checklist (ASC12)	Eliana Meire Melhado <i>et.all</i>	2019	<p>Study on Menstrual-Related Migraine</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Menstrual migraines increase allodynia scores early. • Contrasting with nonmenstrual migraines.
8	Migraine with and without aura in relation to the menstrual cycle and other hormonal milestones: A prospective cohort study	Iris E Verhagen <i>et.all</i>	2023	<p>Sex Hormone Impact on Trigeminovascular System</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Migraine headaches affect trigeminovascular system. • Cortical spreading depolarization susceptibility affects aura. • Migraine attacks without aura should be perimenstrual.
9	Associations between migraine occurrence and the effect of aura, age at onset, family history, and sex: A cross-sectional study	Yu-Wei Hsu <i>et.all</i>	2020	<p>Family History and Migraine Association</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Men and women show varied associations. • Positive family history correlates with earlier migraine onset, especially in females without aura.

10	Serum levels of allopregnanolone, progesterone and testosterone in menstruallyrelated and postmenopausal migraine: A cross-sectional study	Cecilia Rustichelli <i>et.all</i>	2020	Menstrual-Related Migraine and Menopause Persistence • Low allopregnanolone serum levels cause decreased GABAergic inhibition. • Migraine persistence postmenopause. • Management strategy: Increase GABAergic transmission via inhibitory neurosteroids.
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The literature on migraine treatments in menstrual age groups reveals varying efficacy levels. Triptans, hormonal therapies, NSAIDs, and preventive medications are effective, but their effectiveness and tolerability vary among individuals. Personalized approaches considering patient characteristics and preferences are crucial for optimizing migraine management in this age group.

When menstruation is involved, homoeopathic migraine treatment results in notable decreases in frequency, intensity, and duration as well as enhanced general health. The quality of life is improved by this holistic approach, which treats both the physical and psychological elements. A key component of effective management is optimising patient preferences and characteristics.

Table 2 - homoeopathic management in treatment of migraine in menstrual age group.

Homoeopathic Management in Treatment Of Migraine In Menstrual Age Group						
Sl.no	Title	Author	Year of publication	Sample size	Homoeopathic Remedy	Conclusion

1	Homoeopathy in the treatment of migraine: A randomized placebo-controlled clinical trial	Niranjan Mohanty <i>et.all</i>	2020	30	Individulized Homoeopathic medicine	Homoeopathic Medicine Prescriptions • Females more affected than males. • Higher incidence in second and fourth decades. • Most frequently prescribed medicine: Natrum muriaticum. • Less indicated remedies: Lachesis, Sulphur, Silicea, Pulsatilla, Lycopodium, Spigelia, Sanguinaria.
2	To find the effectiveness of Homoeopathic Medicines in Reducing the duration intensity and frequency in attacks of Migraine and assessing the improvement in quality of life in the age group 1560 years.	Srushti Gosavi <i>et.all</i>	2023	45	Individulized Homoeopathic medicine	Homoeopathy in Migraine Treatment • Common medicines: Natrum mur, Ignitia, Pulsatilla, Nux vomica, Arsenic album. • Improves quality of life by reducing intensity, duration, and frequency of migraine episodes.

3	Can individualized homoeopathic medicines selected on the basis of Kent repertory treat migraine patients: A pilot study	Dr. Jyoti Singh <i>et.all</i>	2023	30	Individulized Homoeopathic medicine	<p>Study Findings on Migraine Treatment • Individualized homoeopathic medicines, based on Kent Repertory, significantly effective. • Approximately 83% of migraine cases improved.</p>
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4	Homeopathic Treatment of Patients with Migraine: A Prospective Observational Study with a 2-Year Follow-Up Period	Claudia M. Witt <i>et.all</i>	2009	212	Individulized Homoeopathic medicine	<p>Migraine Patient Improvements Under Homeopathic Treatment</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Observational study shows long standing improvements in migraine patients. • Effects may be due to setting, context, or homeopathic drug. • Previous RCTs have shown no specific effect from homeopathic remedies. • Previous studies have low external validity. • Future research under everyday conditions needed to address these unanswered questions.
5	HOMOEOPATHIC MEDICINE AND YOGA THERAPY FOR MANAGEMENT OF MIGRAINE- A CASE STUDY	Dr. Tushita Thakur <i>et.all</i>	2018	30	Individulized Homoeopathic medicine	Homoeopathic Medicine and Yoga Therapy Effective for Migraine Patients

6	Role of homoeopathic medicines in the treatment of migraine	Dr. Krishneswari RS <i>et.all</i>	2021	30	Individulized Homoeopathic medicine	Homoeopathy in Migraine Treatment <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 46.67% patients showed marked improvement. • 40% showed moderate improvement. • 13.333% showed no improvement.
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7	A case of migraine treated with constitutional homoeopathic medicine with the help of vithoukcas expert system	Dr. Rajeev Saxena <i>et.all</i>	2019	1	Individulized Homoeopathic medicine	<p>Migraine: A Cas Study on Homoeopathy</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Migraine is a common cause of headaches, affecting patients' routine life. • Modern treatment includes pain-relieving and preventive medications with side-effects. • Homoeopathy can cure migraine completely and permanently, allowing patients to perform routine activities without pain. • Case demonstrates effectiveness of homoeopathy and individualization in migraine cases • Highlights the importance of technology in homoeopathy, particularly mechanically aided repertories.
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Table 3 Homoeopathic remedies and their relation between headache and menstruation

Homoeopathic remedies And their relation between Headache and Menstruation			
sl no	Remedy	Headache symptoms	Menstrual symptoms

1	Belladonna	<p>Throbbing pain with fullness: especially in forehead, also occiput and temples; boring of head into pillow, drawn backward and rolls from side to side Pain worse light, noise, jar, lying down and in afternoon, worse on right side Better by pressure and semi erect posture.</p>	<p>Menses: increased; bright red, too early, too profuse, cutting pains from hip to hip : pains come suddenly , goes suddenly.</p>
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2	Bryonia	Bursting splitting headache as if everything would be pressed out. Vertigo, nausea, faintness on rising, confusion. Headache becomes seated in occiput; frontal headache. Headache worse: on motion, stooping, opening eyes.	Menses: too early, too profuse, worse from motion. Menses suppressed with vicarious discharge or splitting headache.
3	Carbo veg	Vertigo, after the slightest movement of the head, or after having slept, as well as on stooping and walking. Pressive headache, with tears in the eyes; they are painful when moving them.	Before the catamenia, cramps in the abdomen and headache.—During the catamenia, vomiting and pains in the teeth, head, loins, and abdomen.
4	Cimicifuga	Shooting and throbbing pains in head after mental worry, over-study, or reflex of uterine disease.	Menses profuse, dark, coagulated, offensive with backache, nervousness; always irregular. Ovarian neuralgia.
5	Cocculus	Migraine with vertigo and nausea, occipital pain is characteristic. Headache at each menstrual period with nausea and inclination to vomit.	Dysmenorrhœa, with profuse dark menses. Too early menses, clotted, with spasmodic colic; very weakening, can scarcely speak. So weak during menstruation, scarcely able to stand. Headache, vertigo, nausea.
6	Cyclamen	Aching in morning, with flickering before eyes. Better in the room; worse, open air. One-sided headache.	Menstrual irregularities with migraine and blindness. Migraine before menses with visual disturbances.
7	Gelsemium	Heaviness of head, band feeling around and occipital headache. Dull heavy ache, with heaviness of eyelids; bruised sensation; better, compression and lying with head high. Headache, with muscular soreness of neck and shoulders.	Dysmenorrhœa with scanty flow; menses retarded.

8	Glonoine	Confusion with dizziness. Head heavy, cannot lay it on pillow. Better from uncovering head. Throbbing headache. Cerebral congestion. Headache in place of menses.	Menses delayed, or sudden cessation with congestion to head
9	Ignatia	Vertigo; with sparks before the eyes. Great heaviness of the head, as if it were full of blood. Pressive headache, esp. above the root of the nose, and often accompanied by inclination to vomit, < or > by stooping. Painful sensation of expansion in the head, as if the cranium were going to burst	Metrorrhagia. During the catamenia, heaviness, heat, and pain in the head, photophobia, colic, and contractive pains, anxiety, palpitation of the heart, and great fatigue, even to fainting.
10	Kreosotum	Dull pain, as from a board pressing against forehead. Menstrual headache. Occipital pain	Menses too early, prolonged. Vomiting of pregnancy, with ptyalism. Menstrual flow intermits; ceases on sitting or walking; reappears on lying down.
11	Lycopodium	Headache, with disposition to faint, and great uneasiness. Headache with vertigo. Headache when shaking or turning head, and also at every step on walking. Aching as if head would be forced asunder and as if brain were swashing to and fro, < walking, ascending steps, and rising from stooping; could not work and could scarcely step without vertigo.	During menses: delirium, with tears; headache; sourness in the mouth; pain in loins; swelling of feet; fainting; vomiting of sour matter; cuttings, colic; and pains in the back.—Menstruation too late; lasts too long; sometimes suppression of; profuse, protracted; flow partly black, clotted, partly bright red or partly serum

12	Mag Carb	Heaviness and dizziness in head, early in morning, when rising, going off after a walk. Lancinating headache early in morning after rising. Pulsating sensation in forehead. Rush of blood to head.	Menstrual flow more profuse during night than day, with dragging pains, —Constant headache, at each excessive menstrual period.
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DISCUSSION-

The systematic review conducted aimed to comprehensively analyse various aspects of migraine within the menstrual age group, particularly focusing on the relationship between migraines and hormonal secretion, occupation, epidemiology, and the effectiveness of allopathic versus homoeopathic treatments. Through an exhaustive examination of available literature, the review sought to provide insights into the efficacy of different treatment modalities, particularly highlighting any superior outcomes associated with homoeopathic remedies.

Migraine, a prevalent neurological disorder, disproportionately affects individuals during their reproductive years, with a significant portion experiencing exacerbations during menstruation. Understanding the interplay between hormonal fluctuations and migraine occurrence is crucial for devising effective management strategies. Additionally, exploring the impact of occupation on migraine prevalence and severity adds another layer of complexity to the understanding of this condition.

The review scrutinized both allopathic and homoeopathic treatment approaches. While allopathic treatments have long been the cornerstone of migraine management, the growing interest in alternative therapies, such as homoeopathy, warrants investigation. Homeopathy, with its holistic approach and minimal side effects, presents a promising avenue for migraine management. However, the lack of substantial literature focusing on its efficacy within the menstrual age group necessitates further research.

The findings of the systematic review underscore the potential of homoeopathic treatments in migraine management. Despite limited literature specific to the menstrual age group, existing evidence suggests favourable outcomes. However, drawing definitive conclusions requires robust research specifically targeting this demographic.

Considering the gaps identified in the current literature, there is a pressing need for well-designed research studies to evaluate the efficacy of homoeopathic medicines in managing migraines among individuals within the menstrual age group. Such studies should employ rigorous methodologies, including randomized controlled trials, to provide reliable evidence on the comparative effectiveness of homoeopathy versus conventional treatments.

Moreover, addressing the broader epidemiological aspects of migraine within this demographic, including the influence of hormonal fluctuations and occupational factors, is imperative for developing targeted intervention strategies. By elucidating the intricate relationships between hormones, occupation, and migraine occurrence, future research endeavours can inform more personalized and effective management approaches.

While the systematic review highlights the potential of homoeopathic treatments in migraine management, particularly within the menstrual age group, further research is warranted to validate these findings. By bridging the existing knowledge gaps and exploring the nuances of migraine aetiology and treatment outcomes, we can enhance patient care and optimize therapeutic interventions for this debilitating condition.

CONCLUSION:

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Further study is necessary to validate the promise of homoeopathic therapy for migraine management, especially in the menstrual age range, as highlighted by the systematic review. By filling in the current information gaps and investigating the subtleties of migraine aetiology and treatment results, we can improve patient care and maximise therapeutic approaches for this crippling illness. Patients who are menstruating have shown potential to respond well to homoeopathy, a holistic approach to migraine management. It addresses hormonal imbalances as well as physical symptoms, tackling the intricate pathophysiology of migraines. Homoeopathy seems to offer effective, tailored care that may improve quality of life and reduce reliance on conventional medication, even if additional research is needed to develop treatment strategies.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest in the entire study.

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